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Review

Public Health Challenges in both Developing and Developed Countries: A review

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Abstract: This paper compares and shows how much more developing countries are more facing public health challenges than developed countries. It presents contributions of the World Health Organization to Public health threats. We also discuss public health challenges that are still rising in both developed and developing countries. Furthermore, this article sheds light on some signs of progress that have been made in public health worldwide by individual countries and/or international organizations. In this review, some solutions and recommendations were suggested to achieve the targeted goals of Healthy people internationally.

Keywords: Public health challenges; Developing countries; Developed countries; Progress.

1. Introduction

There is a big challenge in public health all over the world, in both developing and developed countries (Lopez, 2005; Lopez et al., 2006; “Obesity and Diabetes in the Developing World — A Growing Challenge,” 2007) Many studies show that public health all over the world is currently facing various threats that lead to serious diseases. Many diseases either treatable and/or chronic ones even death have decreased human life expectancy. In this regard, various researches indicated that the world is experiencing such threats unequally. Developing countries are experiencing public health issues more than developed countries. Despite the World Health Organization (WHO) trying to fight against public health issues all over the world, there are still some public health threats facing today’s world (Moters & Europe, 2000). The United Nation's Millennium Development Goals were introduced as a philosophical successor of the World Health Organization’s health for all (United Nations, 2015). It envisaged the overall development as the result of improvement in health, education, environmental sustainability, gender equality, poverty eradication, and international co-operation.

In addition, clear patterns in health care organizations exist among some less-developed countries. There also exist wide variations and gaps in the health resources and administration in less-developed countries (Sreelakshmi & Anish, 2013). These variations and gaps are more pronounced in less-developed than in developed countries. Countries with such unstable health care infrastructure, are often dependent on aid from international organizations. It is of great importance to understand the type of issues these countries are presently facing and how the international community is responding to these issues (Sudarmono, 2019).

The acceptance of the principle of Primary Health Care by the World Health Organization has spearheaded many activities towards achieving its goal of Health for All by 2000 (Moters & Europe, 2000). For example, Eradication of smallpox by an international campaign in 1977 and massive achievements in the control of communicable diseases had kindled a lot of hope regarding the future of health. Even though the member countries of the World Health Organization formulated their health policies according to the broad vision of health for all 2000, the campaign was not successful in bridging the big health gap across the world (United Nations, 2015). Furthermore, the health sector does not have an independent existence. It is closely related to other sectors such as; education and agriculture. Interestingly, the commission on social determinants of health by the international health organization, explained how the health of individuals and

communities are affected by inputs from other developmental sectors (Determinants & Report, n.d.). Unhealthy can be tackled effectively if only social determinants are working together. Diseases are distally determined by some social factors and poor health which may lead to unfavorable social conditions. They act as a vicious cycle, whereby, the development of other related sectors becomes inevitable for health progress in a given community.

Poverty is a social evil related to ill health across the world observed in developing countries. The modern epidemic of Human Immunodeficiency Virus-Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome (HIV-AIDS), has been a striking example of this mechanism. Some studies conducted in Africa, have shown that the poorer population sections have a much higher risk of contracting HIV than the non-poor community (Magadi, 2013). Gentilini et al. described the devastating impact of HIV on socioeconomic conditions. This mechanism has played a definite role in blowing up the disease burden into epidemic proportions. Some countries like; Scandinavian countries and Sri Lanka set positive examples, whereby, the better health nurtured by the community has given its toll on overall social development (World Bank Group et al., 2015). However, the challenges facing today's world in the sector of public health are much more complex than we may think.

In this paper, we will, therefore, discuss the challenges in the public health field now being faced by both developing and developed countries, and give an overview of international assistance initiatives as attempted solutions on progress.

2. Public health challenges

2.1 Maternal and child health including vaccine-preventable diseases

The indicators of maternal health are considerably varying all over the world. In developed nations, the maternal mortality ratio averages found to be at 13/100,000 live births in the developing world, which is 440 for the same denominator. Figure 1 shows the causes of maternal deaths worldwide (WHO, 2005). Generally, the infant mortality rate in developing countries seems to be continuously declining (Leon, 2007). However, 35% of Africa's children are at high risk of immature death today, as compared to 10 years ago (*The global burden of disease 2004*, 2004). Almost half of all deaths among children under 5 occur in this region, where improvement has slowed down due to lack of preventive care and treatment, fragile health systems, and socioeconomic stagnation caused by conflicts, political instability, and HIV/AIDS (Ayieko et al.,

2012; Fernandes et al., n.d.; Landes et al., 2012; Maclennan et al., 2013) Table 1 is showing the achievements measured by infant mortality rate, in the past 45 years which are much less than other countries with comparable economies. Less-developed countries have not achieved what the developed countries achieved 50 years back.

Figure 1. Annals of Medical & Health Sciences Research. Adapted from Holmes et al. (2004)

Table 1: Trend in Infant Mortality Rate in some countries of the World

Countries	Infant Mortality Rate per 1,000 live births		percentage change
	1960	2005	
india	235	56	76.0
china	210	23	89.0
Sri lanka	140	12	91.4
Sub Saharan Africa	251	99	60.6
Developed countries	36	7(USA)	80.6

Adapted from: World Bank development report 1960 and WHO report 2005.

It is evident that the political will and leadership are very important parameters to make palpable progress in maternal and child health issues, it is also worth noting that the majority of child deaths worldwide are attributed to very few conditions such as pneumonia, malnutrition, diarrheal diseases and measles, malaria (Rudan et al., 2008) [Figure2].

Figure 2: The majority of child deaths Worldwide. Adapted from Miller et al. (2006)

2.3 Poverty and Nutrition

Malnutrition is still a major cause of death among children under the age of 5 years. On the other hand, poverty is considered as the most potent determinant of infant mortality. In this context, the United Nations has set the reduction of extreme poverty and hunger as the first goal in MDG. It has been reported that malnutrition in children leads to unhealthy, due to communicable diseases especially to diarrheal diseases and pneumonia (Thörn et al., 2011). By contrast, pieces of evidence are accumulating that undernourished children are more prone to non-communicable diseases such as diabetes in their future life (Sreelakshmi & Anish, 2013). Thus, it might be logical to believe that the millions of children under starvation because of economic deprivation and political instability all over the world will affect the global burden of diseases even at their adulthood.

Food safety has also become a worldwide concern, particularly in African and Asian countries, especially because of climate change (Lloyd et al., 2011). The economic crisis and the political instabilities in these countries make the situation worse, whereby, millions of people are still struggling to get a single meal per day. Paradoxically, the beginning of the millennium has witnessed a paradigm shift in the food crop utility. On the other hand, many reports revealed the use of more food grains for energy production in developed countries. It is a shame that food materials are used as fuels when about 1 billion people globally are living in extreme poverty on an income of below \$1 a day (Moda, 2019).

2.4 Health Translation

Health translation might be explained as changes in health that follow an identifiable pattern that occurs over a relatively long period of time (Cohen et al., n.d.). These changes include the pattern of disease, disabilities, death as well as changes in the type of organized social response to health conditions. Transformation is more complex in middle-income countries where social inequalities are deep. Infectious diseases have lost their previous predominance but still, maintain a high position in the epidemiologic profile. Similarly, the absolute and significant increase of non-communicable diseases and injuries was observed. Another significant attribute of the transition is that it is not always unidirectional from communicable to non-communicable diseases. A reversal of trend known as “counter transition” is occurring in some areas e.g. AIDS, TB, and arboviral diseases.

2.5 Emergence of non-communicable diseases

The increased mortality from non-communicable diseases in the Third World countries is reflecting shifting patterns of lifestyle. Ischemic heart and cerebrovascular diseases combined constitute 16% of deaths in 15-59 years age group (Lopez et al., 2006). The number of diabetic patients would be doubled by the first quarter of the century to 366 million, greatly outnumbering the population growth (“Obesity and Diabetes in the Developing World — A Growing Challenge,” 2007). Cancer has raised as one among the major killer diseases, apart from mental diseases and suicides [table 2] (Lopez, 2005). Furthermore, health problems caused by visual impairment, war, accidents, war, injuries, unhealthy lifestyle, and work-related problems, war, and terrorism seem to be a big challenge now as shown in Table 2 (Lopez, 2005).

Table 2: Disease burden Assessed in Disability Adjusted life years (*DALY*)

Rank	1990	2020 (projected)
1	Lower respiratory tract infection	ischemic heart diseases
2	Diarrheal diseases	Unipolar depression
3	Darental conditions	Road traffic accident
4	Unipolar depression	Cerebrovascular accidents
5	Ischemic heart diseases	COPD
6	Cerebrovascular accidents	Lower respiratory tract infection
7	Tuberculosis	Tuberculosis
8	Measles	War
9	Road traffic accident	Diarrheal diseases
10	Congenital Abnormality	HIV

COPD: Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Diseases, HIV: Human Immunodeficiency Virus, DALY: Disability Adjusted Life Years.

2.6 HIV/AIDS, tuberculosis and Malaria

The leading causes of deaths in the developing countries clearly indicate the socio-economic backwardness prevailing in those areas. After pneumonia and diarrheal diseases, HIV/AIDS has emerged as the most common cause of mortality in developing countries (*The global burden of disease 2004*, 2004). It has become one of the leading causes of mortality among adults aged 15-59 years (Lopez et al., 2006). The development of drug resistance has emerged as a big challenge for HIV and Tuberculosis. The emergence of HIV-AIDS had made the burden of tuberculosis more intense and complicated. Resistance to conventional anti-tuberculosis drugs is well-documented. However, the emergence of resistance to the 2nd line drugs, the extensively drug-resistant, and totally resistant tuberculosis (Abubakar et al., 2013; Michael & John, 2012) Tuberculosis, which is considered to be virtually untreatable, has added much burden to the already challenging scenario (Heemskerk et al., 2015; Li et al., 2013) The statistics available in the World Health Organization's regional data strongly confirm the existing health gap between countries [Table 3] (World Health statistics, 2018). Malaria is another major problem from which half of the world population is suffering and it causes about 3,000 deaths every day. The deaths are mostly caused

by a single species, *Plasmodium falciparum*. The burden of Malaria is perpetuated by increasing drug and insecticide resistance. Recent reports indicate that there are countries where death rate due to Malaria is as high as 2.4 per 1,000, which is comparable to the overall death rate of some developed countries. The highest death rate caused by Malaria has been observed in African with a median of 94 per 100,000 populations (World Health statistics, 2018).

Table 3: Global burden of Tuberculosis and HIV across the World Health Organization regions

World Health Organization Regions	Morbidity in terms of prevalence per 100.000Population		Cause-specific mortality population
	TB without HIV infection (all age)	HIV (15-49 years)	TB without HIV infection
AFRICA	475[398-563]	4.5 [4.5-5.0]	52 [48-58]
AMERICA	38 [30—48]	0.5 [0.4-0.6]	2.1 [1.8-2.8]
SOUTHERN-EAST ASIA	278 [186-398]	0.3 [0.3-0.3]	27 [2.-35]
EUROPE	63 [49-81]	0.4 [0.3-0.4]	6.9 [5.7-8.3]
EAST MEDITERRANEAN	174 [[116-253]	0.2 [0.2-0.2]	6 [5.6-7.4]
WESTERN PACIFIC	160 [107-231]	0.1 [0.1-0.1]	13 [10-17]

Adapted from WHO: World Health Organization, TB: Tuberculosis, HIV: Human Immunodeficiency Virus

2.7 Emergence of new mosquito-borne diseases

The emergence of arboviral infections caused by the widened geographical distribution of *Aedes* mosquitoes is the hallmark of the transition. The World is experiencing a pandemic of Chikungunya along with dengue (Fritz et al., 2019; Gould et al., 2010) Multiple factors including climate change, movement of people, lack of environmental sanitation, and enhanced adaptability of vectors make all communities vulnerable to such infections.

2.8 Equity related issues and deprivation

Globalization and neo-liberalization have definitely improved the average health indicators. However, it has also led to the existing wide health gap across countries, adding on to the health inequities existing worldwide. This inequity is linked to economic deprivation, gender status, ethnicity, and cultural alienations. The poor are often kept away in terms of access and provision of health-related services both in quality and quantity. Equity-related issues exist even in basic amenities of human life such as food and water. For some individuals and communities, there is no food or resources that can be translated to food grains and some available food (Wahlqvist et al., 2009). Compared to other goods and services, the cost of food is very high. It requires as much attention as it was perceived at Alma-Ata (Motors & Europe, 2000).

2.9 Globalization

All around the world, social and economic integration has accelerated in the past decade. The World health organization report 2008 observes that “Globalization is putting the social cohesion of many countries under stress”. This has had indirect and direct consequences on health both in terms of non- communicable and communicable diseases (Sheehy & Sharma, 2013). One example of such effect is on the epidemiology of communicable diseases, opening of travel and trade routes between countries has been accompanied by the spread of diseases and their vectors (Tatem & Hay, 2007). At the same time, changing international rules concerning patent protection has decreased access to essential medicines which widened the inequity related to health services delivery (“Promot. Access to Med. Technol. Innov.,” 2013).

2.10 Financial and Economic issues

In India, the data of national sample survey organization 42nd round showed that the contribution of the Central Government in the health field is only 1.65% of gross national product, and it provides only for 11.84% of the total health care expenditure (“Promot. Access to Med. Technol. Innov.,” 2013). This bleak picture is repeated in almost every developing country. The health care expenditure is dominated by the private sector in India and most of the African countries which put much of the burden on citizens through out-of-pocket treatment expenditure. Assistance from public funding and strategies of risk pooling are rudimentary in these settings, which make the public vulnerable to catastrophic health expenditure. As compared to the affording sections that

are covered by private or social insurance schemes, the underprivileged sector of the community is forced to make direct payments and is in a constant threat of heavy debts as public provision is grossly inadequate (Gwatidzo & Stewart Williams, 2017). Financing in the health sector is currently getting more and more complex in that external donors support the type of activities directed to achieve their vested interests. This process leads to a prioritization of health services that are different from the local needs.

2.11 Environment related issues

“Protecting health from climatic change” was the theme of world health day 2008. World Health Organization has listed down the impact of climate change on health (World Health Organization, 2011). Extreme air temperatures and pollution, Floods, droughts and contaminated water raise disease risk. Climatic effects on agriculture lead to a high increase in malnutrition cases. Moreover, a more extreme and variable climate can destroy houses, communities, and lives.

2.12 The nexus between climate change, migration, and health

With traditional landscapes and livelihoods of entire communities being increasingly threatened by climate change and extreme weather events, there is a pressing need to study the effect on population displacement and human migration. The first illustrated publication mapping this complex phenomenon describes the multiple factors at play and the challenges and highlights the opportunities (Of et al., n.d.).

Figure 3 summarizes, in broad terms, the relationships that are considered to operate: climate change has indirect and direct effects on population movement (H. L. F. Cooper et al., 2015; Matlin et al., 2018), and also on health (Introduction et al., 2019; McAdam, 2011) while the migration is in itself a risk factor for adverse health events (L. A. Cooper et al., 2018). As pointed out by Beck, the multiple and diverse factors are all connected together in complex ways (Migration & Portal, 2018).

An example: **links between climate change, health, and migration**

3. Progress in Public Health.

Even though there are still some threats in public health but many studies show that there is also good progress as well. According to Dr. Martin Luther King, Jr (letter from Birmingham Jail, April 16, 1963), (Secretariat et al., 1989), “injustice anywhere is a threat to justice everywhere.” It means that it is better to strive for health equity in both developed and developing countries. Health disparities are avoidable inequalities in health between groups of people within countries and between countries” (The World Health Report HEALTH SYSTEMS FINANCING, n.d.), they reflect social injustice because these differences in health across groups are not avoidable (Justice & Equity, 2020).

Health equity is “when every person has the opportunity to attain his or her full health potential and no one is disadvantaged from achieving this potential because of social position or other socially determined circumstances” (Bharmal et al., 2015). Achieving equity in health requires a

societal willingness to address challenges associated with the social determinants of health. Those challenges include racism, bigotry, lack of public safety, residential segregation, poverty, low-quality education, substandard housing, limited employment opportunities, etc. (Bharmal et al., 2015; Williams, 2001)

Appreciable thing is that progress is increasing for instance during the past 30 years, dramatic progress in health status and reductions in infant and premature mortality have been achieved in the United States. However, differences in life expectancy between educational and income groups have increased (Bharmal et al., 2015; Chetty, Stepner, et al., 2016; Future et al., 2002) rates of mortality and morbidity among some minority groups, including African American, American Indian/Alaska Native, and low-income white people, are comparable with rates of people living in low- and middle-income countries (L. A. Cooper et al., 2018).

3.1 Collaborations among researchers, educators, and Practitioners

To achieve equity, researchers, educators, and practitioners should engage in efforts to enhance strategic thinking, disruption to current approaches and norms based on evidence. Several opportunities and barriers exist in the following types of collaborations. An example of a successful academic-community partnership is the Johns Hopkins Center for Health Equity Community Advisory Board. During the past 8 years, this diverse and inclusive group of stakeholders has developed several effective interventions to reduce disparities in hypertension control in a population in Baltimore and it is now beginning to translate and disseminate these programs locally, nationally and globally (L. A. Cooper et al., 2016). Besides, a community-based dietary intervention involving collaboration with a local grocer was developed and successfully piloted (Hyochol Ahn, PhD, Michael Weaver, PhD, Debra Lyon, PhD, Eunyoung Choi, RN, and Roger B. Fillingim, 2017). This intervention has now been translated into African Americans with hypertension and kidney disease, a population at high risk for poor clinical results (Martins et al., 2012). Several clinic-based interventions were also developed through this partnership (L. A. Cooper et al., 2013; Ephraim et al., 2014) One was Project Reducing Disparities and Controlling Hypertension in Primary Care, a cost-effective care-management intervention that took place from 2012 to 2015. This program has achieved substantial progress in blood pressure reduction among African American and white patients (Hussain et al., 2016; Willink et al., 2020). Another one is an ongoing, large, pragmatic clinical trial comparing the effectiveness of enhanced usual care plus audit, feedback, and education with care provided by a collaborative care team. The collaborative care intervention incorporates community health worker support and/or specialist consultation. In addition, it is expected to reduce ethnic/racial disparities in hypertension control among patient participants at 30 clinics in Maryland and Pennsylvania (L. A. Cooper et al., 2018).

3.2 Training and Education

Training and educating a diverse group of public health in transdisciplinary methods is significant to address the health equity crisis. It is particularly significant that people from disadvantaged communities cultivate their interests and talents in this work given their personal experiences that confer unique expertise in the realities of implementing, developing and evaluating health equity interventions. Even though evidence of the effectiveness of training programs is limited, several best practices exist (L. A. Cooper et al., 2018; Golden et al., 2015; Maxson & Mitchell,

2016) These programs incorporate experiential and didactic opportunities in multidisciplinary areas. These areas may include health services research, social epidemiology, implementation science, behavioral science, intervention development, evaluation science, community-based participatory research, quality improvement, and health policy research. Evidence of the effectiveness of training in communication skills, teamwork, cultural competency, and leadership skills is also limited (Birkhäuser et al., 2017; Depalma, 2000) However, the best practices strengthen trainees understanding of the ways in which social determinants of health influence the ability of families and individuals from disadvantaged communities to engage in healthy behaviors. Many programs also provide practitioners and researchers with service-learning opportunities in community settings to develop skills in program implementation, policy development, and evaluation.

3.3 Policy Translation

The field of public health needs practitioners who understand the social determinants of health and can connect the dots from research to policy program implementation by advocating for the incorporation of health effects into policy evaluations. Achieving health equity involves research examining how policies and programs in sectors ranging from housing to immigration produce both unintended and intended consequences for health. For instance, the study by Roche et al (2015) (L. A. Cooper et al., 2018) examined the real-time mental health effects of changes to immigration enforcement policies in the United States in recent years. The results of their study revealed that these policies were associated with an increased likelihood of psychological distress among Latino parents of adolescents, which in turn might negatively affect the health and well-being of their children (L. A. Cooper et al., 2018). Thus Public health practitioners must advocate for such research and ensure that it informs policy development and implementation.

Cross-sector policies, such as those addressing consumption of sugar-sweetened beverages and housing mobility programs, are significant for addressing major public health threats such as cardiovascular disease and obesity (Ludwig et al., 2012; Veerman et al., 2016). Yet a lack of political will and challenges to funding can hinder efforts to disseminate such approaches and expand them to scale to meet population needs. The relationship between health equity and policy translation is complex and necessitates interactive evaluation. For instance, nutrition policies to improve healthful food in schools can reduce obesity risk among children (Defend & Food,

n.d.). However, such policies do not address the broader social context of segregation and concentrated poverty that negatively affect the health of children and economic trajectories over time (Chetty, Stepner, et al., 2016; L. A. Cooper et al., 2018) An effort such as Health Impact Assessment and program evaluation is important for policy development and long-term assessments of how policies produce unintended outcomes for population health and health equity (Chetty, Hendren, et al., 2016; H. L. F. Cooper et al., 2015; L. A. Cooper et al., 2018)

3.4 Longevity

Improved methods to assess health and disease, growth of analytic capacity, tools, and technological advances in chemistry and biology, have all made possible progress in the life span of the average US resident. Longevity in the United States and other industrialized nations has increased more in this century than in any past century by a wide margin. In 1900 average longevity was 47 years (Cho et al., 2015). In 1996 it had increased to 76.1 years, a remarkable 62% increase (World Health Organization & OMS, 1998). Improvements are equally striking for the older population whereby an individual reaching age 65 in 1900 could expect to live an additional 11.9 years. That expectancy increased to 17.5 years by the early 1990s, a 47% increase (Agrawal, 2016). While these statistics are mirrored in many developed countries, we have reminders of the fragility of these improvements. Many sub-Saharan African countries are in the process of precipitous increases in mortality due to the devastation of AIDS. The dissolution of the Soviet Union led to a precipitate drop of 6 years in male life expectancy due to increases in social disintegration, poverty, and environmental pollution (Little, 1998).

3.5 Reduced Toll of infectious diseases

Public health measures like water, safe food, and development of immunizations against many serious diseases such as polio and smallpox, coupled with enhanced economic conditions, are together credited with substantial reductions in the burden of infectious diseases (Casper et al., 2017; “Editorial Board,” 2007). However, globalization of food supply, growing antibiotic resistance and appearance of new diseases, especially HIV infection, increase the toll of infectious agents.

3.6 Reduction in Chronic Diseases Mortality

Identification of the precipitating mechanisms for chronic diseases responsible for a high percentage of premature deaths has led to effective global health and medical interventions to reduce their mortality rates. For instance, public health organizations joined organized medicine in developing effective programs to find and treat those with high blood pressure and abnormal lipid profiles and to decrease tobacco use. Age-adjusted cardiovascular mortality rates have declined 30%–50% from their peak in most well-industrialized countries, including the United States (Schwartz & Sheps, 1999). Declines in cerebrovascular death rates are even sharper than for cardiovascular disease in the United States. However, public health efforts to address other crucial proximate determinants of major chronic disease risk factors like lack of adequate physical activity and unhealthful nutrition have been unsuccessful.

3.7 Risk factor reduction: the example of Tobacco control

The history of tobacco control exemplifies the threats and successes of American public health in the twentieth century. Reduced tobacco use has made a substantial contribution to the decline of cardiovascular diseases, many cancers and respiratory diseases (Byeon, 2015). Cigarettes use increased from almost zero in 1900 to a peak of 4345 cigarettes per capita in 1963. Although some public health officials suspected a strong link between tobacco use and diseases, it was not until the late 1950s that a sufficient body of epidemiologic studies was accumulated to mount a public health information program, culminating in the first Surgeon General's report on Smoking and health in 1964 (Satcher et al., 1999).

The prolonged multifaceted efforts to reduce tobacco use have reduced prevalence rates to about 25% of adults, with per capita consumption in 1997 down 45% from peak levels. However, smoking among youth and college students is registering rapid increases. Between 1991 and 1997, the prevalence of smoking increased from 21% to 30% among tenth graders [88]. New tactics, including state initiatives to tax tobacco, proceed for control efforts and litigation, culminating in the 1998 settlement. Tobacco companies would pay \$206 billion over 25 years with few restrictions on how money could be used, suggested the need for broad coalitions with common objectives and a wide range of policy and political tactics.

3.8 Alcohol and Illicit drugs

With the exception of the short-lived period of prohibition, during which alcohol consumption fell significantly, control efforts have been of uneven effect. More recent control efforts, especially efforts to change policies like excise taxes, advertising restrictions, and warnings have been largely unsuccessful (Jernigan & Ross, 2020). An exception is the significant achievement of a decline in alcohol-related traffic fatalities, with a 32% drop between 1982 and 1999 attributed to reductions in legal blood alcohol concentrations for drivers, increases in minimum legal drinking age, etc. (DeJong & Hingson, 1998). Control of illicit drugs should be considered as a failure in the 20th century. We have succeeded in good estimating of their toll and unlocking how they affect brain chemistry, but neither prevention effort nor border control has convincingly altered their impact.

3.9 Vaccines

Vaccines of high effectiveness now exist for most infectious diseases that caused significant mortality and morbidity at the beginning of the century. Vaccines are credited with virtually eliminating polio in this nation and with accelerating the decline of many other diseases ranging from diphtheria and tetanus to hepatitis A and B (Apostolopoulos et al., 2016).

In this century for the first time, a smallpox disease was eradicated from the entire planet. The vanquishing of this scourge was a triumph of epidemiology and of worldwide cooperation among global health and other governmental organizations. This success has emboldened public health leaders to target other diseases for near-term eradication of measles in the United States and polio worldwide. National Immunization Days have proved quite effective in third world countries, capped by polio vaccination of 119 million children in India in a single day (Aylward et al., 2000).

3.10 Environmental and Occupational Health

Michael Gochfeld and Bernard Goldstein (Gochfeld & Goldstein, 1999) reported that environmental health, almost synonymous with sanitation in the early part of the century, contributed to substantial reductions in vaccine-preventable diseases long before vaccines were available.

3.11 HIV transmission

Elimination succeeded within some geographic regions by mode of transmission is defined as a reduction of incidence to zero. Unlike with eradication, the disease-causing agent continues to persist in the population and prevention efforts are crucial to ensure that elimination persists. Elimination of incident infections could thus theoretically be achieved even as HIV prevalence persists, using existing prevention methods such as treatment (Kevin Range, 2012), pre-exposure prophylaxis (Baeten et al., 2012; Shrestha et al., 2016) condoms (Jones et al., 2019), voluntary medical male circumcision (Auvert et al., 2005; Gray et al., 2007) harm reduction (*Reporting on HIV and Drug Use in Myanmar*, n.d.), and opioid substitution programs (Mukandavire , C ., Low , A ., Mburu , G ., Trickey , A ., May , M ., Davies , C ., ... Vickerman , P . 2017).

Due to sexual behavior and injection drug use, HIV transmission can be controlled. However, its elimination is not currently realistic in that the number of transmissions is considerably higher and the structural opportunities for intervention do not exist. A realistic objective will, therefore, be epidemic control. Many prevention tools, both new and old, are available to reduce HIV transmission due to these risk behaviors. The effectiveness of Antiretroviral therapy (Kevin Range, 2012) and pre-exposure prophylaxis (Grant et al., 2014; Shrestha et al., 2016), in addition to condom use (Holmes et al., 2004; Mofenson et al., 2009), needle and syringe exchange programs (Woodak & Cooney, 2004), and VMMC (Gray et al., 2007), (Auvert et al., 2005) in reducing the risk of HIV transmission was observed. This demonstrates that existing methods have the potential to greatly reduce HIV transmission. Delivering these tools in combinations, monitoring the uptake in target populations, and monitoring for inequities in uptake will be important to maximize their impact.

3.12 HIV mortality

Given current treatment options, the elimination of HIV mortality should be an aspirational yet feasible goal. Combination antiretroviral therapy with substantial adherence has been shown to be effective in reducing viral loads and extending the life span of persons living with HIV (May et al., 2014). Expanding testing programs to identify all persons contracted with HIV followed by treatment initiation and adherence support for those persons who are diagnosed could lead to the elimination of mortality due to AIDS-related complications. Deaths from HIV-related causes

should be treated as sentinel events, instigating a public health investigation to understand the factors leading to treatment failure. In 2017 there were approximately 940,000 AIDS-related deaths globally (UNAIDS, 2019). Appropriate resources will need to be made available to investigate the complex, multilevel failures that likely contribute to HIV-related mortality, like; limited healthcare access, substance use, mental health problems, and poverty. Compiling country-level data from all over the world, the Joint United Nations Program on HIV/AIDS (UNAIDS) has summarized improvement through the end of 2017 (DATA, 2017).

3.14 Migrants and refugees Health

The large increase in displaced persons, refugees, and migrants seen in 2014–2016 brought a new urgency to global efforts to achieve equity in access to health services. At the 69th World Health Assembly in May 2016, member states overwhelmingly supported the vision of a future where all people have equal access to quality health services. These services, are co-produced in a way that meets their life course needs, coordinated across the continuum of care, and are comprehensive, effective, timely, acceptable, efficient and safe (WHO, 2019). Implementation of this vision needs to be addressed and includes the health needs of migrants. World Health Organization emphasizes that the access of migrants and refugees to quality, essential health services are of paramount significance to rights-based health systems, to public health security and to public efforts aimed at reducing health inequities (WHO, 2017a). It, however, notes that access to health services is affected by stigma, social exclusion, poverty, discrimination, cultural differences language, separation from family and socio-cultural norms, financial and administrative hurdles and lack of legal status (WHO regional office for Europe, 2017).

World health organization has observed that there is a need for reliable global data on migration and health, especially in relation to undocumented migrants and those not accessing formal services (WHO regional office for Europe, 2017). In May 2017, resolution world health Assembly 70.15 on ‘Promoting the health of migrants and refugees’ was endorsed at the 70th World Health Assembly (WHO, 2017b). The resolution urges the Member States and requests world health organizations to identify and collect evidence-based information, best practices, experiences and lessons learned on addressing the health needs of migrants and refugees. This was done in order to contribute to the development of a draft global action plan on promoting the health of migrants and refugees, to be considered for adoption at the 72nd World Health Assembly in 2019 and to

report back to the world health assembly. World health organization instituted an online survey, inviting the Member States, institutions, civil society groups, networks, individuals and relevant organizations involved in migrants' and refugees' health, to offer relevant information, lessons learned and examples (WHO, 2017b).

Furthermore, the health of migrants often remains marginal in broader discussions on migration, and migrants are a frequently forgotten population in health strategies. However, with increasing acceptance by states of their responsibility for ensuring the health and human rights, fears about challenges of infection are gradually giving way to desire to treat both communicable diseases and the broader health problems of arriving refugees and migrants. Annex II of the New York declaration set in motion a process of intergovernmental consultations and negotiations culminating in the planned adoption of a global compact on Migration at an intergovernmental conference on international migration in 2018 (Kam et al., 2018). However, specific reference to health is missing among the areas for attention in the global compact that are highlighted (Planning & Division, 2017). In UN General Assembly Resolution A/71/L.58.IOM argues that health is a core cross-cutting theme in the follow-on to the New York declaration and points out that there is a clear normative framework for the rights of refugees and migrants to health without discrimination (International Organization for Migration & OIM, 2018; United Nations Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2017). World health organization supports policies that provide health services to refugees and migrants, irrespective of their legal status (Matlin et al., 2018).

Courses and Facilities that provide training in refugees and migrant health can be found in many countries, including, Australia (Emami et al., 2009), Canada (Jock, 2015) and the USA (Mental & Certificate, 2012). In Europe, in addition to training and education available at the national level, at the regional level, there are training modules provided under the EC CARE program. WHO-EURO operated its first Summer School on migrants and Refugee Health as an intensive 5-day course, 'managing the public health aspects of migration', in Italy in July 2017 (Mental & Certificate, 2012). It aimed to improve participants' knowledge and understanding of the main health issues and needs of migrants and refugees.

4. Conclusion and Future Perspectives

Focusing on risk rather than diseases might be a better way to address global health challenges. Furthermore, primordial prevention should be given emphasis because the interventions in the distal determinants of health are more significant in sustaining the health and development of a country. Another suggestion is that it should focus on the comprehensive all-inclusive health of the community rather than the conventional maternal and child health-centered approaches. Commitment to value different forms of knowledge is required to promote learning that treats and rethinks traditional practice within global systems. In addition, blending global knowledge with on-the-ground innovations from the third world countries will surely transform future modes of international cooperation and any benefits accruing therefrom. However, our understanding of innovation diffusion processes between developing and developed countries is fragile, and the existing literature on this phenomenon is limited. The global commitment to ending the HIV epidemic, exemplified through the United Nations' Political Declaration on HIV and AIDS, indicates a high degree of motivation from countries all over the world to reduce mortality and morbidity caused by HIV/AIDS. Let us hope that the new initiative and the true spirit of the public health care concept will help humanity to confront public health threats in both developed and developing countries in a better way. There is a hope for sustainable all-inclusive development through a decentralized and democratic process. Public health care is the way that we have in order to achieve a healthy life.

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Dedication

Not mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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